

Synthesis of α -(3-Ethyl-4-methoxyphenyl)alkylamines

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Synthesis of α -(3-ethyl-4-methoxyphenyl)alkylamines with alkyl groups as *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl, and *n*-hexyl as potential amoebocides is described.

'Kachru and Pathak' synthesised β - and α -(2-alkyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)ethylamines for testing them as potential amoebocides. The amoebocidal activity in both the series was observed to increase with alkylation¹. Kachru and Sawhney² prepared α -(3-alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)ethylamines for the same purpose. In these compounds also *in vitro* activity increased with the increase in molecular weight. Based on these observations, it was considered worthwhile to prepare structural analogues of the above mentioned amines with different alkyl groups attached to the basic nitrogen atom and to examine their amoebocidal activity.

Three α -(3-ethyl-4-methoxyphenyl)alkylamines (II) with R as ethyl, *n*-propyl, and *n*-amyl have been synthesised for the purpose according to the following route:

The amines will be tested for their amoebocidal activity.

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1. This Journal, 1957, 34, 611, 768.

2. Kanahwa, J. Sci. Ind. Res., 1957, 34, 768.

3. This Journal, 1959, 36, 121, 486.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Ethyl-4-methoxypropio-phenone (I: R=Et).—Propionyl chloride (23 g.) and CS_2 (200 ml) were cooled to 0° in a r.b. flask equipped with a reflux condenser and a CaCl_2 guard tube. Powdered anhydrous AlCl_3 (54 g.) was added portionwise to this mixture with constant shaking and cooling. *o*-Ethylanisole (27 g.) was then slowly run in from time to time while the flask was maintained at 0° . After the initial reaction had ceased, the flask was left overnight for the reaction to proceed. Next day the contents were refluxed on a steam bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. CS_2 was distilled and the residue decomposed with crushed ice and HCl (conc.). The product was extracted with benzene and the extract was successively washed with water, a 10% NaOH solution, and water.

From alkaline washings, the demethylated product was obtained as a solid on acidification. It was methylated in the usual manner with dimethyl sulphate and KOH , extracted with benzene, and washed with water.

The combined benzene solution was dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 . After removal of the benzene, the residual liquid was distilled under vacuum. The ketone distilled at $145\text{--}47^\circ/3$ mm, yield 31 g. (81%). (Found: C, 75.32; H, 8.12. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 74.97; H, 8.39%).

Its 2,4-*DNP* was prepared and crystallised from acetic acid in red needles, m.p. 155° .

The *semicarbazone* was prepared and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 175° . (Found: N, 16.70. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 16.86%).

3-Ethyl-4-methoxy-n-butyrophenone (I: R=*n*-Pr).—B.P. $162^\circ/6$ mm. (Found: C, 75.40; H, 9.01. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 75.69; H, 8.80%).

Its *semicarbazone* was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 148° . (Found: N, 15.82. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 15.96%).

3-Ethyl-4-methoxy-n-caprophenone (I: R=*n*- C_5H_{11}).—B.P. $182^\circ/7$ mm. (Found: C, 76.70; H, 9.62. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.88; H, 9.46%).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared and crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 120° . (Found: N, 14.21. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 14.43%).

α -(3-Ethyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-propylamine (II: R=Et).—B.P. $139\text{--}40^\circ/8$ mm, yield 39%, based on the ketone. The *amine picrate* was prepared and crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 162° .

The *amine hydrochloride* was prepared by adding dry ether, saturated with HCl gas, to the ethereal solution of the amine. It was crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and anhydrous ethanol, m.p. 215° . (Found: N, 6.19; Cl, 15.50. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{ONCl}$ requires N, 6.10; Cl, 15.46%).

α -(3-Ethyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-butylamine (II: R=*n*-Pr).—B.P. $145\text{--}50^\circ/8$ mm, yield 46%. The *amine picrate* was crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 171° . The *amine*

*Melting and boiling points are uncorrected.

hydrochloride was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and anhydrous ethanol, m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 5.67; Cl, 14.46. $C_{13}H_{22}ONCl$ requires N, 5.74; Cl, 14.57%).

α -(3-Ethyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-hexylamine (II: R=*n*- C_5H_{11}).—B.P. 160-65°/8 mm, yield 63%. The *amine picrate* was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 172°. The *amine hydrochloride* was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 209°. (Found: N, 5.25; Cl, 13.18. $C_{13}H_{26}ONCl$ requires N, 5.15; Cl, 13.07%).

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Received June 23, 1964.